

Ternary Complexes : Equilibrium Studies of Mixed-Ligand Complexes of Nickel Ion with Some Carboxylic and Phenolic Acids**

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Manuscript received 25 January 1978, accepted 10 April 1978

The mixed-ligand chelates of nickel ion with aspartic, glutamic, thiodiglycolic, thiodipropionic, malonic, malic, 5-hydroxysalicylic and 3, 5-dinitro salicylic acids have been investigated at 30° and $\mu=0.1M(\text{NaClO}_4)$ by pH metric method. Ni^{+2} forms 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates with aspartic and glutamic acids and only 1 : 1 chelates with the remaining chelating agents, the mixed-ligand chelates being formed in a simultaneous and stepwise equilibria. Negative $\Delta \log K$ values for all the systems except glutamic-thiodiglycolic, malic-thiodipropionic, malic-thiodiglycolic and malic-3, 5-dinitro salicylic acids are ascribed to their differences in ring sizes. Intermediate $\Delta \log K$ values are expected when one of the ligand is carboxylic and the other phenolic acid.

A perusal of literature¹⁻⁴ shows that Ni^{+2} forms binary and ternary complexes with carboxylic and phenolic acids and Ni^{+2} complexes of thiocompounds have been reported biologically active⁵. A review of Sigel⁶ clearly brings out biological importance and applications of simple and mixed complexes of Ni^{+2} with some selected ligands.

The present work is a continuation of our earlier work⁷ and was undertaken with a view to find out whether Ni^{+2} forms complexes with the ligands chosen in a simultaneous or stepwise equilibria when (i) both the ligands are carboxylic, (ii) one of them is carboxylic and other phenolic and (iii) both the ligands are phenolic acids.

Experimental

The ligands aspartic, glutamic, thiodiglycolic, thiodipropionic, malonic, malic, 3, 5-dinitrosalicylic

and 5-hydroxysalicylic acids were obtained from Fluka (Germany). These ligands were purified by repeated crystallisation and their purity was checked by their melting points. Nickel nitrate (AnalaR) was used for the preparation of metal solution and the concentration of nickel ion in the original solution was estimated by EDTA titrations⁸. The details regarding other chemicals, the experimental procedure involved in the potentiometric titration and the pH measurements are described in an earlier communication from this laboratory⁹.

Results and Discussion

The dissociation constants of the ligands and the stability constants of nickel complexes were calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti^{10,11}. The presence or absence of 1 : 2 complex was established by the procedure of Ramamoorthy and

TABLE-1 LOGARITHMS OF EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF TERNARY COMPLEXES OF NICKEL ION-PRIMARY(H_2Y)-SECONDARY(H_2X) ACIDS

Acid/Systems	Temp. = 30 ± 0.1°		$\mu=0.1M(\text{NaClO}_4)$			$\Delta \log K$
	β_{XY}	K_{DXY}^a	K_{2XY}	K_{2YX}	K_{MX_1}	
glutamic [*] -malonic	8.59	+0.51 ^b -0.99	2.97	4.63	3.96	-0.99
glutamic-thiodiglycolic	11.26	+2.96 ^b +1.40	7.08	5.64	4.18	+1.40
aspartic ^{**} -thiodipropionic	5.92	-0.95 ^b -2.81	-1.20	4.31	1.61	-2.81
malic [@] -thiodipropionic	5.52	+0.62	3.91	2.23	3.29 [@]	+0.62
malic-thiodiglycolic	9.02	+1.55	4.85	5.73	-	+1.55
malic-3, 5-dinitrosalicylic	7.44	+0.04	4.15	3.33	4.11	+0.04
3, 5-dinitrosalicylic-5-hydroxysalicylic	12.86	-0.65	3.46	8.75	9.40	-0.65

^{*}log $K_1=5.62$; log $K_2=4.12$, ^{**}log $K_1=7.12$; log $K_2=5.27$.

$K_{DXY}^a = K(\text{MX} + \text{MY} \rightleftharpoons \text{MXY} + \text{M})$; $K_{DXY}^b = K(\text{MX} + \text{MY}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{MXY} + \text{MY})$.

The accuracy of β_{XY} values was between 0.01-0.10 log units. - pK values are taken from Ref. No. 7.

** Presented at the 65th session of Indian Science Congress.

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Santappa^{1,2}. Though the formation of mixed-ligand complex was concluded initially from qualitative evidence, Carey and Martell's^{1,3} procedure was adopted to probe into the nature of the mixed-ligand complex and complexation equilibria. The mixed-ligand stabilities and other equilibrium constants were calculated by the procedure^{1,4} and are set out in Table 1. All the mathematical calculations were carried out on MOSCAL 1080S SCIENTIST.

The possible complexation of mixed-ligand systems of nickel ion are given as :

The disproportionation constants

for corresponding systems have been calculated.

The titration curves of pH vs volume of alkali for one representative system are shown in Fig. 1. The moles of base added after the neutralization of HClO₄ are presented as *m*.

Fig. 1. Nickel ion-glutamic-malonic acid system.

$\mu = 0.1M(\text{NaClO}_4)$, $t = 30^\circ$, pH titration curves of system. (i) HClO₄ (1), (ii) HClO₄ + glutamic acid (2), (iii) HClO₄ + glutamic acid + nickel ion (3), (iv) HClO₄ + malonic acid (4), (v) HClO₄ + malonic acid + nickel ion (5) and (vi) HClO₄ + glutamic acid + malonic acid + nickel ion (6) against 0.38 sodium hydroxide.

c = composite curve.

Ni²⁺-glutamic(H₂Y)-malonic(H₂X) acid system :

The pH of precipitation of mixed-ligand system was 8.9 while Ni²⁺-malonic acid complex precipitated at 8.4. No precipitation was observed in Ni²⁺-glutamic acid titration even up to pH 9. Glutamic acid forms both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes in the pH range 3.0-6.5. The formation of 1 : 1 with malonic acid takes place around 4.5 pH. The mixed-ligand titration curve was towards right-hand side of the composite curve in the pH range 3.5 to 5.5 at which $m = 1-3$. The buffer region $m = 0-1$ is due to the dissociation of first -COOH group of malonic acid ($pK_1 = 2.66$). The ligand malonic acid is represented as HX^- . Since the mixed-ligand curve did not coincide with either of the individual metal titration curves, the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 complex by a simultaneous equilibrium was inferred. The complexation reaction may be represented as :

The negative $\Delta \log K$ values of ternary systems indicate that primary and secondary ligand dianions form ternary complexes preferentially to the binary ones. In the present investigation, the mixed-ligand chelates are formed by simultaneous and stepwise equilibria. In glutamic-thiodiglycolic and malic-3, 5-dinitrosalicylic acid system, the mixed-ligand chelate is formed by equilibrium :

It is observed (Table 1) that $\Delta \log K$ values are negative for glutamic-malonic, aspartic-thiodipropionic and 5-hydroxysalicylic-3, 5-dinitrosalicylic acid systems and positive for all the remaining systems. The higher stabilities of Ni²⁺-glutamic-malonic and Ni²⁺-malic-thiodiglycolic than Ni²⁺-aspartic-thiodipropionic and Ni²⁺-malic-thiodipropionic acid systems may be ascribed to the differences in ring sizes of the chelates. In aspartic-thiodipropionic and malic-thiodipropionic acid systems, comparatively less strain involved in the ten membered ring formed by thiodipropionic acid may be responsible for the observed lower value and further confirmed by its lowest value in the binary complex ($\log K = 1.61$). Though the mixed-ligand stability can be explained as due to (i) nature of donor atoms, (ii) ring size formed by the ligands, (iii) neutralization of charge in the ternary complex or (iv) steric hindrance in one of the binary complexes, our study revealed that the ring sizes formed by the two ligands are predominantly responsible for the stabilized or destabilized nature of the ternary complexes studied.

The carboxylate oxygen is not directly bound to the benzene nucleus like phenolic oxygen. The carboxylate oxygen may, therefore, adjust stereochemically more easily than the phenolate ion which is directly attached to the benzene nucleus. In the present case, greater strain in Ni-O is, therefore, expected when the phenolate oxygen is coordinated to the central metal ion when the coordination takes place through the carboxylate

oxygen. The electron affinity of the phenolate oxygen will be higher than that of carboxylate oxygen. The coulombic repulsion between the ends oxygen will, therefore, be more when both ligands are phenolic acids than when they are carboxylate ones. Hence it is expected that the values of $\Delta \log K$ should be higher when both the ligands are phenolic than when both of them are carboxylic acids and an intermediate value is to be expected when one of them is carboxylate and other a phenolic acid. The observed value of $\Delta \log K$, in the present investigation, fit into this pattern very well.

The values of K_{DXY} run parallel to $\Delta \log K$ in all the systems for the equilibrium $MX + MY \rightleftharpoons MXY + M$. In the case of glutamic-thiodiglycolic and glutamic-malonic systems $K_{DXY} > 0.6$ log units for the equilibrium $MX + MY \rightleftharpoons MXY + M$, indicates a preferential formation of ternary complexes over 1:2 binary complexes. The comparison of K_{LYX} and K_{MX_1} shows that the ternary complexes are more stable as compared to the binary^{15,16}.

Acknowledgement

Authors wish to thank Dr. D. V. Jahagirdar, Reader, Department of Chemistry, for his suggestions in the present work.

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